

HOLY FNMTC-BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- MAY 2019
RM 15: NORMAL PUERPERIUM (HMDW 046)
TIME ALLOWED: 2HOURS

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTIONS ONE

Under physiology of the new born explain the following

- a. Digestive system - 7 marks
- b. Reproductive system - 7 marks
- c. A woman had SVD at your facility and you did first examination on the new-born. Three days later you visited the woman. Give **six (6)** specific observations you will during examination - 6 marks

QUESTIONS TWO

Explain the following

- a. Endocrine activity - 7 marks
- b. The Involution of the uterus - 13marks

QUESTIONS THREE

- a. Madam Paulina delivered 8 hours ago and to be discharged home. Items for baby bath set and procedure for baby bath explained to mother. Outline the steps involves in baby bathing - 12 marks
- b. State **FIVE** ways to prevent heat loss in a new-born - 5 marks
- c. Withdrawal is one of the family planning methods mention the **other 3** - 3 marks

QUESTIONS FOUR

- a. Outline **FIVE** management of sore nipple - 5 marks
- b. State **TWO** advantages and **TWO** disadvantages each of infant formula - 4 marks
- c. Do cord dressing, preparation done, hands washed and dried sterile gloves put on continue from here - 6 marks
- d. State any **five (5)** management of leg cramps in the puerperal woman - 5 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....

HFNMTC – BEREKUM CAMPUS

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - MAY 2018

POST NAC/NAP RMP 123 PHYSIOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT OF NORMAL PUERPERIUM AND NEONATE

TIME ALLOWED: 45 MINUTES.

- *Answer all questions.*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate booklet*
- *Each question carries 20marks*
- *Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.*

Question One

Madam Bosoma , 32 year old primipara delivered at your clinic with episiotomy done and was discharged the following day. She reported after 24 hours with the complains of inability to urinate since she went home.

- a. State FIVE(5) general causes of retention of urine in the puerperium - 5 marks
- b. State FIVE (5) clinical manifestation of urine retention in a normal puerperal woman - 5 marks
- c. Describe your management of Madam Bosoma - 10 marks

Question Two

Explain the physiological changes of the following

- a. Urinary system - 10 marks
- b. Uterus - 10 marks

Question Three

Madam Salamatu delivered 2hours ago and the baby was classified as a normal baby by the midwife.

- a. Describe the essential care the baby needs within the first two hours - 10 marks
- b. Under essential new born care, what would be the management of the baby after being classified as normal before Discharge - 5marks
- c. What TEN (10) things would you look for in your first examination of the head of the newborn? -5 marks

Question Four

- a. Outline the procedure in cord dressing - 10marks
- b. Mention FIVE (5) signs and symptoms of breast engorgement in the puerperal woman - 5marks
- c. Mention FIVE(5) reflexes that would be exhibited by a newborn - 5marks

NMTC-BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS , DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION, MAY 2016
RM -12 HMDW 046 NORMAL PUERPERIUM
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HRS

QUESTION ONE

Madam Mercy G4P3 delivered 48hours ago and complained of constipation and varicose veins at the limbs identify one problem.

- a. State a strength for the problem you choose (1mark)
- b. Draw a comprehensive nursing care plan for madam Mercy up to evaluation (15marks)
- c. State four (4) complication of urine retension (4marks)

QUESTION TWO

- a. Explain the physiological changes that occurs in the uterus during puerperium (7marks)
- b. Enumerate the THREE criteria for LAM selection? (3 marks)

Mrs Owusu Ansah Para 4 delivered in the maternity unit in your hospital and came for first postnatal visit (9th day post-delivery). On abdominal palpation the uterus was palpable and was as measured 8cm.

- c. State 3causes of her disorder (3marks)
- d. Describe your management to Mrs Owusu Ansah (7marks)

QUESTION THREE

A client delivered 2 minutes ago at your facility

- a. Describe how you would maintain the new born's temperature during the first hour? (4marks)
- b. Conduct examination on the new born baby's head only (first examination) 12 mark
- c. Mention four (4) changes which may occur in the stools of the new born within the first week of life

(4 marks)

QUESTION FOUR

A puerperal woman came for both first and second postnatal visits in your facility.

- a. Outline 5 differences between first and second examination on the mother and three (3) differences on the baby (8 marks)
- b. Enumerate three (3) key points you should note before bathing a baby for the first time. (3 marks)
- a. Mention four (4) ways to prevent infection on the new born (4 marks)
- c. Outline any FIVE (5) management of breast engorgement? (5 marks)

HF NMTC-BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION DECEMBER-2016
RM 13 RMD 222 THE NORMAL PUERPERUM AND THE NEONATE
TIME ALLOWED 2Hr
ESSAY

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

QUESTION ONE

Madam Bosoma, 32 year old primipara delivered at your clinic with episiotomy done and was discharged the following day. She reported after 24 hours with the complains of inability to urinate since she went home.

- a. State FIVE(5) general causes of retention of urine in the puerperum - 5 marks
- b. State FIVE (5) clinical manifestation of urine retention in a normal puerperal woman - 5 marks
- c. Describe your management of Madam Bosoma to relieve the retention - 10 marks

QUESTION TWO

Baby Kyereme was delivered 90 minutes ago and was classified by the midwife as a normal baby.

- a. Outline EIGHT (8) normal characteristics on the newborn skin that differentiate it from an adult - 8 marks
- b. Mention FOUR(4) factors that influence birth weight - 4 marks
- c. What FOUR(4) factors can cause BabyKyereme to vomit within the first 48 hours - 4 marks
- d. Mention FOUR (4) Anti- infective factors of breast milk - 4 marks

QUESTION THREE

Explain the physiological changes of the following

- a. Urinary system - 10 marks
- b. Uterus - 10 marks

QUESTION FOUR

- a. Outline the procedure in cord dressing - 15 marks
- b. In examination of a puerperal woman, mention FIVE (5) important areas you will assess and a simple reason. - 5 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
HOLY FAMILY NUSING AND MIDWIFERY TRAINING COLLEGE - BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY 2018
RM 14 PHYSIOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT OF NORMAL PUERPERIUM AND NEONATE

TIME: 2HRS.

ESSAY

- *Answer all questions.*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate booklet*
- *Each question carries 20marks*
- *Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.*

Question One

Baby Kyeremaa was delivered 90 minutes ago and was classified by the midwife as a normal baby.

- a. Outline EIGHT (8) normal characteristics on the newborn skin that differentiate it from an adult - 8 marks
- b. Mention FOUR(4) factors that influence birth weight - 4 marks
- c. What FOUR(4) factors can cause Baby Kyeremaa to vomit within the first 48 hours - 4 marks
- d. Mention FOUR (4) Anti- infective factors of breast milk - 4 marks

Question Two

- a. Describe how you would express and save breast milk for a baby's use - 10 marks
- b. State TWO (2) characteristics of a baby who is well attached to the breast - 2 marks
- c. State FOUR(4) contraindications of breastfeeding - 4 marks
- d. State TWO (2) immunizations that are given at birth and their route of administration - 4marks

Question Three

Madam Kyeremaa had a normal delivery and was educated on postnatal exercise on discharge.

- a. What Five (5) benefits will Madam Kyeremaa get from performing the postnatal exercise? - 5marks
- b. What Ten (10) findings will the midwife note during the first examination of Madam Kyeremaa's baby under the following headings:
 - i. Upper extremities - 5marks
 - ii. Genitalia - 5marks
- c. List Five (5) reflexes that will ascertain that the baby is a normal baby. - 5marks

Question Four

Explain the physiological changes of the

- a. Uterus of the puerperal mother - 10 marks
- b. Gastro intestinal tract of the baby - 10 marks

NMTC - BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY - 2013
RM - 9 MANAGEMENT OF NORMAL PUERPERIUM
TIME ALLOWED: 1½ Hrs.

ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

Mrs. Tweneboa had spontaneous vaginal delivery (SVD) of a male child on Friday. Examination of the newborn is to be carried on baby Kofi who was born 20 minutes ago with A/S 9/10 10/10.

- a. Examine the following areas of the baby for 10 marks
- | | | |
|-----------|---|---------|
| Scalp | - | 2 marks |
| Eyes | - | 2 marks |
| Mouth | - | 2 marks |
| Abdomen | - | 2 marks |
| Genitalia | - | 2 marks |
- b. How will you manage the women for first 18 hrs. after delivery? - 10 marks

Question Two

- a. Describe two (2) specific care you will render to a woman and her baby who fivisited your clinic for 2nd postnatal visit
- | | | |
|---------------|---|---------|
| i. Mother (2) | - | 4 marks |
| ii. Baby (2) | - | 4 marks |
- b. Give six (6) benefits of breastfeeding - 6 marks
- | | | |
|-------------|--|--|
| 3 to mother | | |
| 3 to baby | | |
- c. Mention and explain simply any three (3) Natural Family Planning Methods - 6 marks

Question Three

- a. Give health education on nutrition to a woman who is about to discharge home- 9 marks
- b. Not less than forty (40) words describe the following;
- | | | |
|---------------------|---|---------|
| i. After pain | - | 4 marks |
| ii. Sub- involution | - | 3 marks |
| iii. Backache | - | 2 marks |
| iv. Constipation | - | 2 marks |

INDEX NUMBER.....

HFNMTC – BEREKUM

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION –OCTOBER 2020

R M 16 PHYSIOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT OF THE NORMAL PUERPERUM AND THE NEONATE RMD 222

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HR

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark

QUESTION ONE

Explain the physiological changes of the following

- a. Urinary system - 6 marks
- b. Uterus - 10marks
- c. State FOUR (4) breastfeeding difficulties of the baby - 4 marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. Mention SIX (6) signs and symptoms of breast engorgement in the puerperal woman - 6 marks
- b. Describe how you would manually express and save breast milk for a baby's use - 10 marks
- c. Mention FOUR (4) Anti- infective factors of breast milk - 4 marks

QUESTION THREE

- a. A first year student approached you and asked about the psychology of the newborn with respect to vision. How would you explain to her? - 7 marks
- b. In examination of the newborn, mention FIVE (5) things the midwife would look for in the mouth - 5 marks
- c. During your education on discharge, you encouraged the puerperal mothers to perform postnatal exercises. What eight (8) importance of postnatal exercise would they benefit? - 8 marks

HFNMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION –OCTOBER 2020
PBM 3 (RMD 222)PHYSIOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT OF THE NORMAL PUERPERUM AND
THE NEONATE
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HR

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark

QUESTION ONE

- a. A first year student approached you and asked about the psychology of the newborn with respect to vision. How would you explain to her? - 7 marks
- b. In examination of the newborn, mention FIVE (5) things the midwife would look for in the mouth - 5 marks
- c. During your education on discharge, you encouraged the puerperal mothers to perform postnatal exercises. What eight (8) importance of postnatal exercise would they benefit? - 8 marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. Outline the procedure for dressing cord with chlorhexidine gel - 8 marks
- b. Focusing on the essential newborn care, Baby Hassan was classified to be normal. What action plan should the midwife follow until discharge - 7 marks
- c. Mrs. Asomah has delivered 8 hours ago and has retention of urine. Mention FIVE (5) causes of urine retention in puerperium - 5 marks

QUESTION THREE

- a. Mention SIX (6) signs and symptoms of breast engorgement in the puerperal woman - 6 marks
- b. Describe how you would manually express and save breast milk for a baby's use - 10 marks
- c. Mention FOUR (4) Anti- infective factors of breast milk - 4 marks

HF NMTC-BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION DECEMBER-2016
RM 13 RMD 222 THE NORMAL PUERPERUIM AND THE NEONATE
TIME ALLOWED 2Hr
ESSAY

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

QUESTION ONE

Madam Bosoma, 32 year old primipara delivered at your clinic with episiotomy done and was discharged the following day. She reported after 24 hours with the complains of inability to urinate since she went home.

- a. State FIVE(5) general causes of retention of urine in the puerperuim - 5 marks
- b. State FIVE (5) clinical manifestation of urine retention in a normal puerperal woman - 5 marks
- c. Describe your management of Madam Bosoma to relieve the retention - 10 marks

QUESTION TWO

Baby Kyereme was delivered 90 minutes ago and was classified by the midwife as a normal baby.

- a. Outline EIGHT (8) normal characteristics on the newborn skin that differentiate it from an adult - 8 marks
- b. Mention FOUR(4) factors that influence birth weight - 4 marks
- c. What FOUR(4) factors can cause BabyKyereme to vomit within the first 48 hours - 4 marks
- d. Mention FOUR (4) Anti- infective factors of breast milk - 4 marks

QUESTION THREE

Explain the physiological changes of the following

- a. Urinary system - 10 marks
- b. Uterus - 10 marks

QUESTION FOUR

- a. Outline the procedure in cord dressing - 15 marks
- b. In examination of a puerperal woman, mention FIVE (5) important areas you will assess and a simple reason. - 5 marks

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION JUNE 2014
RM – 10 NORMAL PUERPERIUM
TIME ALLOWED: 2 Hrs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. Outline the immediate care you will render to a newborn after birth. - 10 marks
- b. List five (5) important things you will look for when examining a periperal woman - 5 marks
- c. Enumerate five (5) characteristics of a normal baby you will like a woman to watch out for - 5 marks

Question Two

- a. Describe the physiological changes that occur in the urinary system during puerperium - 10 marks
- b. Outline five (5) management strategies for vomiting in the newborn - 5 marks
- c. State two (2) immunizations that are given at birth and their route of administration - 2 marks
- d. List three (3) causes of breastfeeding difficulties in the newborn - 3 marks

Question Three

The survival of a newborn is said to be mostly dependent on the care of the midwife. (Immediate care /essential newborn care)

- a. State and explain the five (5) most impotent care every newborn baby needs - 10 marks
 Postpartum blues has other names and it is said to be an emotional state experience by some women during first 14 days after delivery with peak at the third and fourth day.
- b. Give ten (10) symptoms of this condition - 5marks
- c. State and give reason, five (5) things you will note when receiving a client from labour ward into lying -in ward - 5 marks

Question Four

Mame Tweneboaa delivered a bouncing baby girl 20 minutes ago with birth weight 3.0kg, A/S 8/10 10/10. You were asked to conduct examination of a newborn on the baby. You visited the woman and her baby 3rd day post delivery and you carried out another examination on the baby.

- a. In your own words of not more than 20 explain the term APGAR score - 1 mark
- b. In a tabular form identify five (5) areas and indicate what you looked for on both examinations - 15 marks

See example below but do not use the example

Area	Initial examination	Subsequent
eye	presence eyeball	jaundice
	color/ blood stain	subsiding blood stain
	Paleness	discharge

- c. Outline FOUR (4) things one should note on the lochia - 4 marks

HF NMTC-BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION DECEMBER-2016
RM 13 RMD 222 THE NORMAL PUERPERUIM AND THE NEONATE
TIME ALLOWED 2Hr
ESSAY

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

QUESTION ONE

Madam Bosoma, 32 year old primipara delivered at your clinic with episiotomy done and was discharged the following day. She reported after 24 hours with the complains of inability to urinate since she went home.

- a. State FIVE(5) general causes of retention of urine in the puerperuim - 5 marks
- b. State FIVE (5) clinical manifestation of urine retention in a normal puerperal woman - 5 marks
- c. Describe your management of Madam Bosoma to relieve the retention - 10 marks

QUESTION TWO

Baby Kyereme was delivered 90 minutes ago and was classified by the midwife as a normal baby.

- a. Outline EIGHT (8) normal characteristics on the newborn skin that differentiate it from an adult - 8 marks
- b. Mention FOUR(4) factors that influence birth weight - 4 marks
- c. What FOUR(4) factors can cause BabyKyereme to vomit within the first 48 hours - 4 marks
- d. Mention FOUR (4) Anti- infective factors of breast milk - 4 marks

QUESTION THREE

Explain the physiological changes of the following

- a. Urinary system - 10 marks
- b. Uterus - 10 marks

QUESTION FOUR

- a. Outline the procedure in cord dressing - 15 marks
- b. In examination of a puerperal woman, mention FIVE (5) important areas you will assess and a simple reason. - 5 marks